

Live Review Timeline & Checklist

Live Reviews are topic-centered, interactive preprint review calls via a video conference tool such as Zoom. Outputs from Live Reviews can be used to improve a manuscript or be integrated into journal review workflows. This document outlines the timeline and checklist we use at PREreview when running a Live Review in collaboration with a partner organization. For more information about Live Reviews please visit <https://prereview.org/live-reviews>

Timeline

The following timeline can be shared with the partner team. Yellow text can be modified to match the partner organization's details.

Week	PREreview Team	Partner Team
Week 0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agree on the event date - Prepare and share the communication plan for advertisement and registration - Prepare and share registration form (PREreview Live Review Zoom Meeting registration with a description of the event and confirmation email sharing expectations with registrants) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicate identified preprint to the PREreview team after confirming the authors' consent - Agree on the event date - Review and provide feedback on the registration form and communication plan
Start of Registration Window		
Week 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Registration - Execute communication plan (i.e., share invites on social media, mail lists, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Execute communication plan (i.e., share invites on social media, mail lists, etc.) - Identify editors who will attend
Week 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare and share the template of the collaborative notes document - Execute communication plan 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review and provide feedback on the collaborative notes document - Execute communication plan
Event		

Week 4	- Host and facilitate the 90-min event - Record event if consent from authors is obtained	- Attend event
Week 5	- Share collaborative review draft with Partner team	- Review and provide feedback on the collaborative review draft
Week 6	- Post review on PREreview.org with names of participants who opted in to be named	

PREreview Team Checklist

When a partner reaches out with a confirmed preprint

- Agree on a date and time that works for both parties
- Confirm facilitators' availability
- Create Zoom registration for the meeting
 - Add a description of the event, logos, custom email confirmation, reminder frequency, and potential questions for participants (e.g., "Would you like to be contacted with invitations to similar events in the future?") ([template](#))
- Share a collaborative Google Drive folder with the partner team including:
 - [Live Review Information Document](#) which can be adapted in agreement with the partner organization
 - Registration form text ([template](#)) and the link to the registration page
 - Communication plan ([template](#))
 - Collaborative Writing document ([template](#))
- Ask partner team to - and add info to the work as soon as received

- Share their logo for the registration form and social media card
- Reach out to the author(s) with the event information, language to invite colleagues ([template](#)), and questions about recording the event (if applicable)
- Select an expert for the call (if applicable)
- Review and add information to the communication plan ([template](#))

After the event

- Download the attendee list from Zoom, and add details to a database (if they have given consent to being contacted)
- Log the number of attendees
- Thank all participants for their participation and offer the opportunity to contribute to the final review or be mentioned as a participant in the Live Review (if applicable)
- Draft the PREreview based on the collaborative review notes

Follow-up

- Thank and share the PREreview with the partner group
- Share the finalized review on [PREreview.org](#)